

On Fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is introduce the notion of fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra, several theorems, properties are stated and proved. The fuzzy relations on KK-algebras are also studied.

Keywords:

ARZ-algebra, fuzzy subalgebra, fuzzy ideal, fuzzy ARZ-ideal, homomorphisms of ARZ-algebras, image and pre-image of fuzzy ARZ-ideals, the Cartesian product of fuzzy ARZ-ideals.

Introduction

A BCK-algebra is an important class of logical algebras introduced by K. Is'eki [8] and was extensively investigated by several researchers. The class of all BCK-algebras is a quasivariety. K. Is'eki posed an interesting problem whether the class of BCK-algebras is a variety. In [9], Y. Komori introduced a new concept of BCC-algebras. In [2-7], W.A. Dudek and X.H. Zhang introduced the notion of BCC-ideals in BCC-algebras and described connections between such ideal and congruences. W.A. Dudek and Y.B. Jun, considered the fuzzification of BCC-ideals in BCC-algebras In ([10,11]), C. Prabpayak and U. Leerawat the notion of KU-algebras. They gave the concept of homomorphism of KU-algebras and investigated some related properties. The concept of fuzzy subset and various operations on it were first introduced by L.A. Zadeh in [13], then fuzzy subsets have been applied to diverse field. The study of fuzzy subsets and their application to mathematical contexts has reached to what is now commonly called fuzzy mathematics. Fuzzy algebra is an important branch of fuzzy mathematics. Since these ideas have been applied to other algebraic structures such as semi-groups, rings, ideals, modules and vector spaces. O.G. Xi, ([12]) applied this concept to BCK-algebra, and he introduced the

notion of fuzzy sub-algebras (ideals) of the BCK-algebras with respect to minimum. In this paper, the study of fuzzy algebraic structures was started with the introduction of the concept of fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebras and then we investigate several basic properties which are related to fuzzy ideals. We describe how to deal with the homomorphism of image and inverse image of fuzzy ideals and ARZ-ideals. We have also proved that the Cartesian product of fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideal is fuzzy ideal and fuzzy ARZ-ideal.

. Preliminaries

Now, we give some definitions and preliminary results needed in the later sections.

Definition 2.1. [1]. An **ARZ-algebra** is a nonempty set X together with a binary internal operation $*$ together with a binary internal operation, for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(i) ((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0,$$

$$(ii) 0 * x = 0,$$

$$(iii) x * 0 = x,$$

$$(iv) x * x = 0,$$

$$(v) x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y.$$

$$(vi) x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x \neq 0 \Rightarrow y * x = x, \text{ where } x \neq 0.$$

We can define a binary relation (\leq) by putting $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x * y = 0$.

Example 2.2. [1]. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	0	a
b	b	b	0	b	0
c	c	c	c	0	c
d	d	d	b	d	0

It is easy to show that $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Proposition 2.3. [1]. In ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the relation defined (\leq) satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- 1) $x \leq y \Rightarrow z * x \leq z * y$,
- 2) $x \leq y \Rightarrow y * z \leq x * z$,
- 3) $(x * y) * z \leq y * z$,
- 4) $(x * y) * (z * y) \leq x * z$

Proposition 2.4. [1]. In any ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

- 1) $(x * y) * y = 0$,
- 2) $x * y = 0$ implies that $0 * x = 0 * y$,
- 3) $x * 0 = y * 0$ implies that $x = y$.

Definition 2.5. [1]. A nonempty subset S of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **subalgebra of X** if $x * y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 2.6. [1]. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra. I is called an **ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$.

Definition 2.7. [1]. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-

algebra. I is called an **ARZ-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in$

*	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0	1
2	2	2	0	0	1	1
3	3	2	1	0	1	1
4	4	4	4	4	0	1
5	5	5	5	5	5	0

X ,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

Example 2.8. [1]. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $I_2 = \{0, 1, 2\}$ and $I_3 = \{0, 1, 2\}$ are ARZ-ideals of X .

Proposition 2.9. [4,7]. In an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$,

- 1- Every ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra is an ideal.
- 2- Every ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra is a subalgebra.

Definition 2.10. [3]. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be ARZ-algebras. A **homomorphism** is a mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ satisfying:

$$f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y), \text{ for all } x, y \in X. \text{ Let } I \subseteq X \text{ and } J \subseteq Y.$$

The image of I of X under f is

$f(I) = \{f(x) \mid x \in I\}$ and **the inverse image of J of Y is** $f^{-1}(J) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \in J\}$. The set $\{x \in X \mid f(x) = 0\}$ is called **the kernel of f** denoted by $\ker f$.

Proposition 2.11. [2]. Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a homomorphism of an ARZ-algebra X into an ARZ-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) $f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) If 0 is the identity in X , then $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .

(3) $x \leq y \Rightarrow f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Theorem 2.12. [2]. Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, '0')$ be a homomorphism of an ARZ-algebra X into an ARZ-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) If I is an ARZ-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is an ARZ-ideal of Y .
- (2) If J is an ARZ-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .
- (3) If I is an ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is an ideal of Y .
- (4) If J is an ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ideal of X .
- (5) $\ker f$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .
- (6) $\text{Im}(f)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

Definition 2.13 ([13]). Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a nonempty set, a fuzzy subset μ of X is a function $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 2.14 ([13]). Let X be a nonempty set and μ be a fuzzy subset of $(X; *, 0)$, for $t \in [0,1]$, the set $\mu_t = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$ is called a **level subset of μ** .

Definition 2. 15. ([11]).

Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, '0')$ be a mapping nonempty sets X and Y respectively. If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset β of Y defined by:

$$f(\mu)(y) = \begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X, f(x) = y\} \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

is said to be the image of μ under f .

Similarly if β is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset $\mu = (\beta \circ f)$ in X (i.e the fuzzy subset defined by $\mu(x) = \beta(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$) is called the pre-image of β under f .

Definition 2.16. ([11]).

A fuzzy subset μ of a set X has sup property if for any subset T of X , there exist $t_0 \in T$ such that $\mu(t_0) = \sup \{\mu(t) \mid t \in T\}$.

3. Fuzzy Subalgebras of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion

called fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to fuzzy subalgebras.

Definition 3.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ in X is called a **fuzzy subalgebra of X** if for all $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Example 3.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0,1\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$I_1 = \{0, 1\}$ is subalgebra of X . Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of ARZ-algebras X .

Theorem 3.3.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of $X \Leftrightarrow$ for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X .

Proof: Assume that μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X . Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy subalgebra, it follows that $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x * y \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is a subalgebra of X .

Conversely, suppose there exist $x', y' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x') < \min \{\mu(x' * y'), \mu(y')\}$.

Putting $t' = (\mu(x' * y') + \min \{\mu(x'), \mu(y')\})/2$, then

$$\mu(x' * y') < t' \text{ and } 0 \leq t' < \min \{\mu(x'), \mu(y')\} \leq 1, \text{ hence}$$

$\mu(x') > t' \text{ and } \mu(y') > t'$, which imply that $(x') \in \mu_{t'}$ and $(y') \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is a

subalgebra, it follows that $x \cdot y \in \mu_t$, and that $\mu(x \cdot y) \geq t$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X . ■

Corollary 3.4.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy subalgebra, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X , when $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$.

Proposition 3.5.

The intersection of any set of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is also fuzzy subalgebra.

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y) &= \inf(\mu_i(x * y)) \\ &\geq \inf(\min\{\mu_i(x), \mu_i(y)\}) \\ &= \min\{\inf(\mu_i(x)), \inf(\mu_i(y))\} \\ &= \min\{(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x), (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. ■

Remark 3.6. The union of two subalgebras is not necessary to be subalgebra as shown in the following example.

Example 3.7. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ and let $*$ be a binary operation defined by the table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	4
2	0	3	0	2	4
3	0	0	2	0	2
4	0	0	0	0	0

It is clear that $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra and $F_1 = \{0,1,4\}$ and $F_2 = \{0, 2, 4\}$ are subalgebras, but $F_1 \cup F_2 = \{0, 1, 2, 4\}$ is not subalgebra, since

$2 \in F_1 \cup F_2$ and $1 \in F_1 \cup F_2$, but $2 * 1 = 3 \notin F_1 \cup F_2$.

Proposition 3.8.

Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra X . The union of its is also fuzzy subalgebra, where $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_{j+1}$, for all $j \in \Lambda$.

Proof. Let $\{\mu_i \mid i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy subalgebras of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$, such that $x, y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ implies that $x \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_j$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Furthermore, let $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_i$ implies that $x \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_i$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Since μ_i is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , it follows that then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_i(x * y) &\geq \min\{\mu_i(x), \mu_i(y)\} \text{ for some } i \in \Lambda \\ \text{Therefore } (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x * y) &\geq \min\{(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x), (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\}, \end{aligned}$$

proving that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X . ■

4. Fuzzy Ideals of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion called fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to fuzzy ideals.

Definition 4.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ in X is called a **fuzzy ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions:

- , for all $x, y, z \in X$,
- (A) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$,
- (B) $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\}$.

Example 4.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	3	3
2	3	3	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0,1\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$I_1 = \{0, 1\}$ is ideal of X . Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebras X .

Example 4.3.

Consider $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ with $*$ defined by the table :

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	a	0	c	b
b	b	c	0	a
c	c	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that

$$\mu(0) = t_1, \mu(a) = \mu(b) = \mu(c) = \mu(d) = t_2, \text{ where } t_1, t_2 \in [0, 1] \text{ and } t_1 > t_2.$$

Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebra X .

Lemma 4.4.

Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and if $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof: Assume that $x \leq y$, then $y * x = 0$, and $\mu(0 * x) = \mu(x)$

$$\geq \min \{ \mu(0 * y), \mu(y * x) \} = \min \{ \mu(y), \mu(0) \} = \mu(y). \text{ Hence } \mu(x) \geq \mu(y). \triangle$$

Theorem 4.5.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \iff$ for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is an ideal of X .

Proof: Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , by (A), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x * y \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x * y) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal, it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(x * y), \mu(y) \} \geq t$ and we have that $x \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (A) and (B) are true. If (A) is false, then there exist

$x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \phi$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is an ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (B) is not true, then there exist $x', y' \in X$ such that,

$$\mu(x') < \min \{ \mu(x' * y'), \mu(y') \}.$$

Putting $t' = (\mu(x') + \min \{ \mu(x' * y'), \mu(y') \})/2$, then

$$\mu(x') < t' \text{ and } 0 \leq t' < \min \{ \mu(x' * y'), \mu(y') \} \leq 1, \text{ hence}$$

$\mu(x' * y') > t' \text{ and } \mu(y') > t'$, which imply that

$(x' * y') \in \mu_{t'}$ and $y' \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is an ideal, it follows that $x' \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Corollary 4.6.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is an ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \phi$.

Proposition 4.7.

Every fuzzy ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Since μ is fuzzy ideal of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then by Theorem (4.5), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . By Proposition (2.9), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X by Theorem (3.3). ■

Theorem 4.9.

Let A be an ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number t in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof: Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Where t is a fixed number in $(0, 1)$. Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$.

If $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$ and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

If $x*y \in A$, then clearly $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

If $x \notin A, y \in A$, then $x*y \notin A$, since A is ideal.

Thus $\mu(x) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Theorem 4.10. Let A be a nonempty subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \Leftrightarrow A$ is an ideal of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x*y \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\} = 1$, and $\mu(x)=1$.

This mean that $x \in A$, i.e., A is an ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose A is an ideal of X , since $0 \in A, \mu(0)=1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$,

If $x \notin A$, then $\mu(x)=0$, and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$.

If $y \notin A$, and $x \in A$, then $(x*y) \notin A$ (since A is ideal).

Thus $\mu(x) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x*y), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Proposition 4.11.

The intersection of any set of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is also fuzzy ideal.

Proof:

Let $\{\mu_i | i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(0) &= \inf(\mu_i(0)) \geq \\ \inf(\mu_i(x)) &= (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) \text{ and} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) &= \inf(\mu_i(x)) \\ &\geq \inf(\min\{\mu_i(x*y), \mu_i(y)\}) \\ &= \min\{\inf(\mu_i(x*y)), \inf(\mu_i(y))\} \\ &= \min\{(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x*y), (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\}. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Remark 4.12. The union of two subalgebras is not necessary to be subalgebra as shown in the following example.

Example 4.13. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and let $*$ be a binary operation defined by the table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	4
2	0	3	0	2	4
3	0	0	2	0	2
4	0	0	0	0	0

It is clear that $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra and $F_1 = \{0, 1, 4\}$ and $F_2 = \{0, 2, 4\}$ are ideals, but $F_1 \cup F_2 = \{0, 1, 2, 4\}$ is not ideal, since $3 * 1 = 2 \in F_1 \cup F_2$ and $1 \in F_1 \cup F_2$, but $3 \notin F_1 \cup F_2$.

Proposition 4.14. Let $\{\mu_i | i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra X . The union of its is also fuzzy ideal, where $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_{j+1}$, for all $j \in \Lambda$.

Proof. Let $\{\mu_i | i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra X , then for any $x, y \in X, i \in \Lambda$, such that $x, y \in \cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ implies that $x*y \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_j$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Furthermore, let $\mu_j \subseteq \mu_i$ implies that $x*y \in \mu_i$ and $y \in \mu_i$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Since μ_i is a fuzzy ideal of X , it follows that then

$$\mu_i(x) \geq \min\{\mu_i(x*y), \mu_i(y)\} \text{ for some } i \in \Lambda$$

Therefore $(\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) \geq \min\{(\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x*y), (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y)\}$, proving that $\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

5. Fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion called fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to

fuzzy ARZ-deals.

Definition 5.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra, a fuzzy subset μ in X is called a **fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: , for all $x, y, z \in X$,

(C) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$,

(D) $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$

Example 5.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	3	3
2	3	3	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is ARZ-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by

$$\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 0.7 & \text{if } x \in \{0,1\} \\ 0.3 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$I_1 = \{0, 1\}$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebras X .

Example 5.3.

Consider $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ with $*$ defined by the table :

*	0	a	b	c
0	0	a	b	c
a	a	0	c	b
b	b	c	0	a
c	c	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu : X \rightarrow [0,1]$ such that

$\mu(0) = t_1, \mu(a) = \mu(b) = \mu(c) = \mu(d) = t_2$, where $t_1, t_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $t_1 > t_2$.

Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy

ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra X .

Proposition 5.4. Let μ be a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and if $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof: Assume that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$, and $\mu(x * 0) = \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x * 0) * y), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(y)\} = \mu(y)$.

Hence $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$. ■

Theorem 5.5.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \Leftrightarrow$ for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof: Assume that μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X , by (C), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $((x * y) * z) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu((x * y) * z) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal, it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x * z \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (C) and (D) are true. If (C) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu_{t'}$ and $\mu \neq \phi$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is an ARZ-ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (D) is not true, then there exist x', y' and $z' \in X$ such that,

$\mu(x' * z') < \min\{\mu((x' * y') * z'), \mu(y')\}$.

Putting $t' = (\mu(x' * z') + \min\{\mu((x' * y') * z'), \mu(y')\})/2$, then

$\mu(x' * z') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min\{\mu((x' * y') * z'), \mu(y')\} \leq 1$, hence $\mu((x' * y') * z') > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that $(x' * y') * z' \in \mu_{t'}$ and $y' \in \mu_{t'}$, since $\mu_{t'}$ is an ARZ-ideal, it follows that $x' * z' \in \mu_{t'}$ and that

$\mu(x' * z') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction.

Hence μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Corollary 5.6.

Let μ be a fuzzy subset of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal , then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is an ARZ-ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \phi$.

Proposition 5.7.

Every fuzzy ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof:

Since μ is fuzzy ARZ-ideal of an ARZ-algebra X , then by Theorem (5.5) , for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ARZ-ideal of X . By Proposition (2.9), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a subalgebra of X .Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of ARZ-algebra X by Theorem (3.3) . ■

Theorem 5.8.

Let A be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number t in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy ARZ-ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof: Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

Where t is a fixed number in $(0, 1)$. Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Let $x, y, z \in X$.

If $((x * y) * z) \notin A$, then $\mu((x * y) * z) = 0$ and so $\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$.

If $((x * y) * z) \in A$, then clearly $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}$.

If $y \notin A, (x) \in A$, then $((x * y) * z) \notin A$, since A is ARZ-ideal. Thus

$$\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(y)\}.$$

Hence μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Proposition 5.9. Let A be a nonempty subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \Leftrightarrow A$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof:

Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $(x * y) \in A$ and $(x) \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\} = 1$, and $\mu(y) = 1$.

This mean that $y \in A$, i.e., A is an ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose A is an ideal of X , since $0 \in A$, $\mu(0) = 1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$,

If $x \notin A$, then $\mu(*x) = 0$, and so $\mu(y) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\}$.

If $y \notin A$, and $x \in A$, then $(x * y) \notin A$ (since A is ideal).

Thus $\mu(y) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(x)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ◻

6. Homomorphism of ARZ-algebras

In this section, we will discuss a new notion called fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras and study several basic properties which are related to fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideals.

Proposition 6.1. Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. An into homomorphic pre-image of a fuzzy subalgebra is also a fuzzy subalgebra.

Proof:

Let β a fuzzy subalgebra of Y and μ the pre-image of β under f , let $x, y \in X$, then we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * y) &= \beta(f(x * y)) \\ &= \beta(f(x) * f(y)) \\ &\geq \min\{\beta(f(x)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(f(x)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, ■

Proposition 6.2. Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. An into homomorphic pre-image of a fuzzy ideal is also a fuzzy ideal .

Proof:

Let β a fuzzy ideal of Y and μ the pre-image

of β under f , then $\beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Since $f(x) \in Y$ and β is a fuzzy ideal of Y , it follows that

$\beta(0') \geq \beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for every $x \in X$, where $0'$ is the zero element of Y .

But $\beta(0') = \beta(f(0)) = \mu(0)$ and so $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for $x \in X$.

Now, let $x, y \in X$, then we get

$$\mu(x) = \beta(f(x))$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \min\{\beta(f(x) * f(y)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(f(x * y)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, This completed the Proof. ■

Theorem 6.3. Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism between KK-algebras X and Y respectively. An into homomorphic pre-image of a fuzzy ARZ-ideal is also a fuzzy ARZ-ideal.

Proof:

Let β a fuzzy ideal of Y and μ the pre-image of β under f , then $\beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Since $f(x) \in Y$ and β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of Y , it follows that $\beta(0') \geq \beta(f(x)) = \mu(x)$, for every $x \in X$, where $0'$ is the zero element of Y . But $\beta(0') = \beta(f(0)) = \mu(0)$ and so $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for $x \in X$.

Now, let $x, y, z \in X$, then we get

$$\mu(x * z) = \beta(f(x * z))$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \min\{\beta((f(x) * f(y)) * f(z)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(f(x * y)), \beta(f(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} \end{aligned}$$

i.e., $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, ■

Proposition 6.4.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. For every fuzzy subalgebra μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of Y .

Proof:

By definition $\beta(y') = f(\mu)(y') = \sup\{\mu(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(y')\}$, for all $y' \in Y$ ($\sup \phi = 0$).

We have to prove that $\beta(y') \geq \min\{\beta(x' * y'), \beta(x')\}$, for all $x', y' \in Y$.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism of ARZ-algebras with sup property, μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X with sup property and β the image of μ under f . Since μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X , for any $x', y' \in Y$, let $x_0 \in f^{-1}(x')$,

$y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that

$$\mu(x_0) = \beta(f(x_0)) = \beta(f(x')) = \sup_{x_0 \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(x_0) \quad \text{and}$$

$$\mu(y_0) = \beta(f(y_0)) = \beta(f(y')) = \sup_{y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(y_0), \text{ then}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(x' * y') &= \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x' * y')} \mu(t) \\ &\geq \min\{\mu(x_0), \mu(y_0)\} \\ &= \min\{\sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t), \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(x'), \beta(y')\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence β is a fuzzy subalgebra of Y . ■

Proposition 6.5.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. For every fuzzy ideal μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y .

Proof:

By definition $\beta(y') = f(\mu)(y') = \sup\{\mu(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(y')\}$, for all $y' \in Y$ ($\sup \phi = 0$).

We have to prove that $\beta(y') \geq \min\{\beta(x' * y'), \beta(x')\}$, for all $x', y' \in Y$.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism of ARZ-algebras with sup property, μ is a fuzzy ideal of X with sup property and β the image of μ under f . Since μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Note that $0 \in f^{-1}(0')$, where 0 and $0'$ are the zero elements of X and Y respectively. Thus

$\beta(0') = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) = \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, which implies that $\beta(0') \geq \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) = \beta(x')$, for any $x' \in Y$

For any $x', y' \in Y$, let $x_0 \in f^{-1}(x')$, $y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x_0 * y_0) &= \beta(f(x_0 * y_0)) \\ &= \beta(f(x' * y')) \\ &= \sup_{x_0 * y_0 \in f^{-1}(x' * y')} \mu(x_0 * y_0) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\mu(y_0) = \beta(f(y_0)) = \beta(f(y')) =$$

$\sup_{y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(y_0)$, then

$$\beta(x') = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) \geq \min\{\mu(x_0 * y_0), \mu(y_0)\}$$

$$= \min\{\sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x' * y')} \mu(t), \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)\}$$

$= \min\{\beta(x' * y'), \beta(y')\}$. Hence β is a fuzzy ideal of Y . ■

Theorem 6.6.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism between ARZ-algebras X and Y respectively. For every fuzzy ARZ-ideal μ of X with sup property, $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of Y .

Proof:

By definition $\beta(y') = f(\mu)(y') = \sup\{\mu(x) \mid x \in f^{-1}(y')\}$, for all $y' \in Y$

($\sup \phi = 0$).

We have to prove that

$$\beta(y') \geq \min\{\beta(x' * y'), \beta(x')\},$$

for all $x', y' \in Y$.

Let $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism of ARZ-algebras with sup property, μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X with sup property and β the image of μ under f . Since μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X , we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$.

Note that $0 \in f^{-1}(0')$, where 0 and $0'$ are the zero elements of X and Y respectively. Thus $\beta(0') = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) = \mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, which implies that $\beta(0') \geq$

$\sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x')} \mu(t) = \beta(x')$, for any $x' \in Y$

For any $x', y', z' \in Y$, let $((x_0 * y_0) * z_0) \in f^{-1}((x' * y') * z')$, $y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')$ be such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu((x_0 * y_0) * z_0) &= \beta(f((x_0 * y_0) * z_0)) \\ &= \beta(f((x' * y') * z')) \\ &= \end{aligned}$$

$\sup_{((x_0 * y_0) * z_0) \in f^{-1}((x' * y') * z')} \mu((x_0 * y_0) * z_0)$ and

$$\mu(y_0) = \beta(f(y_0)) = \beta(f(y')) =$$

$\sup_{y_0 \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(y_0)$, then

$$\beta(x' * z') = \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(x' * z')} \mu(t)$$

$$\geq \min\{\mu((x_0 * y_0) * z_0), \mu(y_0)\}$$

$$= \min\{\sup_{t \in f^{-1}((x' * y') * z')} \mu(t), \sup_{t \in f^{-1}(y')} \mu(t)\}$$

$$= \min\{\beta((x' * y') * z'), \beta(y')\}.$$

Hence β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of Y . ■

7. Cartesian Product of Fuzzy ideal

In this section, we will discuss, investigate a new notion called Cartesian product of fuzzy ideals, fuzzy ARZ-ideals and we study several basic properties which related to fuzzy ideals and fuzzy ARZ-ideals.

Definition 7.1 ([10,11]).

A fuzzy relation R on any set S is a fuzzy subset $R: S \times S \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 7.2 ([10,11]).

If R is a fuzzy relation on sets S and β is a fuzzy subset of S , then R is a fuzzy relation on β if $R(x, y) \leq \min\{\beta(x), \beta(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Definition 7.3 ([10,11]).

Let μ and β be fuzzy subsets of a set S . The Cartesian product of μ and β is defined by $(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) = \min\{\mu(x), \beta(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Lemma 7.4 ([10,11]).

Let μ and β be fuzzy subsets of a set S . Then,

- (1) $(\mu \times \beta)$ is a fuzzy relation on S ,

(2) $(\mu \times \beta)_t = \mu_t \times \beta_t$, for all $t \in [0,1]$.

Definition 7.5 ([10,11]).

If β is a fuzzy subset of a set S , the strongest fuzzy relation on S , that is, a fuzzy relation on β is R_β given by $R_\beta(x, y) = \min \{ \beta(x), \beta(y) \}$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Lemma 7.6 ([10,11]).

For a given fuzzy subset β of a set S , let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on S , then for $t \in [0,1]$, we have $(R_\beta)_t = \beta_t \times \beta_t$.

Proposition 7.7.

For a given fuzzy subset β of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X . If β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, then $R_\beta(x, x) \leq R_\beta(0,0)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof: Since R_β is a strongest fuzzy relation of $X \times X$, it follows from that,

$$R_\beta(x, x) = \min \{ \beta(x), \beta(x) \} \leq \min \{ \beta(0), \beta(0) \} = R_\beta(0,0)$$

, which implies that

$$R_\beta(x, x) \leq R_\beta(0,0). \blacksquare$$

Proposition 7.8. For a given fuzzy subset β of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X . If R_β is a fuzzy ideal (fuzzy ARZ-ideal) of $X \times X$, then $\beta(x) \leq \beta(0)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof: Since R_β is a fuzzy ideal (fuzzy ARZ-ideal) of $X \times X$, it follows from (A),

$R_\beta(x, x) \leq R_\beta(0,0)$. Where $(0,0)$ is the zero element of $X \times X$. But this means that, $\min \{ \beta(x), \beta(x) \} \leq \min \{ \beta(0), \beta(0) \}$ which implies that $\beta(x) \leq \beta(0)$. ■

Remark 7.9.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be ARZ-algebras, we define $(*)$ on $X \times Y$ by: for all $(x, y), (u, v) \in X \times Y$, $(x, y) * (u, v) = (x * u, y * v)$. Then clearly $(X \times Y, *, (0,0'))$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Proposition 7.10.

Let μ and β be fuzzy ideals of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof:

Note first that for every $(x, y) \in X \times X$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(0,0) &= \min \{ \mu(0), \beta(0) \} \\ &\geq \min \{ \mu(x), \beta(y) \} \\ &= (\mu \times \beta)(x, y) . \end{aligned}$$

Now let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(x_1, x_2) &= \min \{ \mu(x_1), \beta(x_2) \} \\ &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \mu(x_1 * y_1), \mu(y_1) \}, \min \{ \beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \min \{ \mu(x_1 * y_1), \beta(x_2 * y_2) \}, \min \{ \mu(x_1), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ (\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2), (\mu \times \beta)(x_1, y_2) \} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(\mu \times \beta)$ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$. ■

Proposition 7.11.

Let μ and β be fuzzy ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof:

Note first that for every $(x, y) \in X \times X$,

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(0,0) &= \min \{ \mu(0), \beta(0) \} \\ &\geq \min \{ \mu(x), \beta(y) \} \\ &= (\mu \times \beta)(x, y) . \end{aligned}$$

Now let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) &= \min \{ \mu(x_1 * z_1), \beta(x_2 * z_2) \} \\ &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \mu((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \mu(y_1) \}, \min \{ \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \min \{ \mu((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2) \}, \min \{ \mu(y_1), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ (\mu \times \beta)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1, (x_2 * y_2) * z_2), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, y_2) \} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(\mu \times \beta)$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$. ■

Theorem 7.12.

Let μ and β be fuzzy subsets of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ such that $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ideal (fuzzy ARZ-ideal) of $X \times X$. Then, for all $x \in X$

- (i) Either $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$.
- (ii) If $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, then either $\beta(0) \geq$

$\mu(x)$ or $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$.

(iii) If $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, then either $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\mu(0) \geq \beta(x)$.

(iv) Either μ or β is a fuzzy ideal (fuzzy ARZ-ideal) of X .

Proof:

(i) suppose that $\mu(x) > \mu(0)$ and $\beta(y) > \beta(0)$, for some $x, y \in X$. Then

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) = \min\{\mu(x), \beta(y)\} > \min\{\mu(0), \beta(0)\} = (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0). \text{ This is a contradiction and we obtain (i).}$$

(ii) Assume that there exist $x, y \in X$ such that $\mu(x) > \beta(0)$ and $\beta(y) > \beta(0)$. Then

$$(\mu \times \beta)(0, 0) = \min\{\beta(0), \beta(0)\} = \beta(0) \text{ it follows that}$$

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x, y) = \min\{\mu(x), \beta(y)\} > \beta(0) = (\mu \times \beta)(0, 0) \text{ . which is a contradiction. Hence (ii) holds.}$$

(iii) is by similar method to part (ii).

(iv) Since by (i) either $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Without loss of generality we may assume that $\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$, from (iii) it follows that either $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ or $\mu(0) \geq \beta(x)$.

If $\mu(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for any $x \in X$, then $(\mu \times \beta)(0, x) = \min\{\mu(0), \beta(x)\} = \beta(x)$. Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$,

since $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, we have

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x_1, x_2) \geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, y_2)\} \text{--- } (\star)$$

If we take $x_1 = y_1 = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(x_2) &= (\mu \times \beta)(0, x_2) \\ &\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(0, x_2 * y_2), (\mu \times \beta)(0, y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mu(0), \beta(x_2 * y_2)\}, \min\{\mu(0), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

This prove that β is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Now, we consider the case $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for

all $x \in X$. Suppose that $\mu(0) < \mu(y)$, for some $y \in X$. then $\beta(0) \geq \beta(y) > \mu(0)$. Since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, it follows that

$$\beta(0) \geq \mu(x) \text{ for any } x \in X \text{ . Hence}$$

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x, 0) = \min\{\mu(x), \beta(0)\} = \mu(x), \text{ taking } x_2 = y_2 = 0 \text{ in } (\star), \text{ then}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x_1) &= (\mu \times \beta)(x_1, 0) \\ &\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, 0), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, 0)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mu(x_1 * y_1), \beta(0)\}, \min\{\mu(y_1), \beta(0)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x_1 * y_1), \mu(y_1)\} \end{aligned}$$

Which proves that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . Hence either μ or β is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Now, $\mu \times \beta$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$, we have

$$(\mu \times \beta)(x_1, x_2) \geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, y_2)\} \text{--- } (\star\star)$$

If we take $x_1 = y_1 = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \beta(x_2 * y_2) &= (\mu \times \beta)(0, x_2 * y_2) \\ &\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)(0, (x_2 * y_2) * z_2), (\mu \times \beta)(0, y_2)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mu(0), \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)\}, \min\{\mu(0), \beta(y_2)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), \beta(y_2)\} \end{aligned}$$

This prove that β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X .

Or taking $x_2 = y_2 = 0$ in $(\star\star)$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x_1 * y_1) &= (\mu \times \beta)(x_1 * y_1, 0) \\ &\geq \min\{(\mu \times \beta)((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), (\mu \times \beta)(y_1, 0)\} \\ &= \min\{\min\{\mu((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta(0)\}, \min\{\mu(y_1), \beta(0)\}\} \\ &= \min\{\mu((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \mu(y_1)\} \end{aligned}$$

Which proves that μ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . Hence either μ or β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Proposition 7.13. Let β be a fuzzy subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X , then β is a fuzzy

ideal of $X \Leftrightarrow R_\beta$ is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof: Assume that β is a fuzzy ideal of X . By Proposition (7.7), we get,

$$R_\beta(0,0) \geq R_\beta(x,y), \text{ for any } (x,y) \in X \times X.$$

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, we have from (B) :

$$\begin{aligned} R_\beta(x_1, x_2) &= \min \{ \beta(x_1), \beta(x_2) \} \\ &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(y_1) \}, \\ &\min \{ \beta(x_2 * y_2), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \min \{ \beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(x_2 * y_2) \}, \\ &\min \{ \beta(y_1), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ R_\beta(x_1 * y_1, x_2 * y_2), R_\beta(y_1, y_2) \} \end{aligned}$$

Hence R_β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$.

Conversely, suppose that R_β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, by Proposition (7.7)

$\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$, which prove (A).

Now, let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2) \in X \times X$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \min \{ \beta(x_1), \beta(x_2) \} &= R_\beta(x_1, x_2) \\ &\geq \min \{ R_\beta((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ R_\beta((x_1 * y_1), (x_2 * y_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ \min \{ \beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(x_2 * y_2) \}, \min \{ \beta(y_1), \beta(y_2) \} \} \end{aligned}$$

In particular if we take $x_2 = y_2 = 0$, then $\beta(x_1) \geq \min \{ \beta(x_1 * y_1), \beta(y_1) \}$.

This proves (B) and β is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Theorem 7.14. Let β be a fuzzy subset of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let R_β be the strongest fuzzy relation on X , then β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \Leftrightarrow R_\beta$ is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

Proof: Assume that β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . By Proposition (7.7), we get,

$$R_\beta(0,0) \geq R_\beta(x,y), \text{ for any } (x,y) \in X \times X.$$

Let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$, we have from (D) :

$$R_\beta(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) = \min \{ \beta(x_1 * z_1), \beta(x_2 * z_2) \}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\geq \min \{ \min \{ \beta((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta(y_1) \}, \\ &\min \{ \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ \min \{ \beta((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2) \}, \min \{ \beta(y_1), \beta(y_2) \} \} \\ &= \min \{ R_\beta(((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2) \} \end{aligned}$$

Hence R_β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of $X \times X$.

Conversely, suppose that R_β is a fuzzy ideal of $X \times X$, by Proposition (7.7)

$\beta(0) \geq \beta(x)$, for all $x \in X$, which prove (C).

Now, let $(x_1, x_2), (y_1, y_2), (z_1, z_2) \in X \times X$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \min \{ \beta(x_1 * z_1), \beta(x_2 * z_2) \} &= R_\beta(x_1 * z_1, x_2 * z_2) \\ &\geq \min \{ R_\beta(((x_1, x_2) * (y_1, y_2)) * (z_1, z_2)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ R_\beta(((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), ((x_2 * y_2) * z_1)), R_\beta(y_1, y_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ \min \{ \beta(((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta((x_2 * y_2) * z_2)) \}, \min \{ \beta(y_1), \beta(y_2) \} \} \end{aligned}$$

In particular if we take $x_2 = y_2 = 0$, then $\beta(x_1 * z_1) \geq \min \{ \beta((x_1 * y_1) * z_1), \beta(y_1) \}$. This proves (D) and β is a fuzzy ARZ-ideal of X . ■

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